

The Tasmania Project

Attitudes towards vaccination and borders in the second year of the pandemic

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As the time for opening borders approaches, The Tasmania Project's fifth general survey (TTP5) asked Tasmanian residents about their experiences of the second year of COVID-19, and their current attitudes to borders, restrictions and vaccination. We also track changing attitudes across the pandemic.

Key Findings

- Half (50%) of respondents agreed that the pandemic had made them reconsider their life priorities, and 43% agreed that they had changed their life priorities due to the pandemic.
- Compared to previous surveys, a lower proportion of respondents agreed that they were enjoying a slower pace of life (43% now vs 60% in previous surveys).
- In-person participation in activities and events was common, but not at pre-pandemic levels. In person in 2021, 75% of respondents had visited a national park or reserve, and 44% and 43% had attended an art exhibition/gallery and live performance, respectively.
- A high proportion (87%) were worried about the rise of political unrest/extremism in Australia. Just under two-thirds (65%) wanted a different Tasmania to emerge from this crisis, and 63% were not confident that we would ever have the same freedoms again.
- Respondents report high levels of compliance with personal COVID-19 safe practices, however, many agree that they have become complacent relative to the start of the pandemic and will be more vigilant once borders open.
- There was no major difference in the proportion of men versus women who were vaccinated.
- To help prevent the spread of COVID-19 in the community, to protect themselves, and to protect their friends and families were the reasons for vaccination selected by the highest proportions respondents.
- Concerns about side effects, testing, and effectiveness at stopping the spread were the most common concerns among the small proportion who were choosing not to get vaccinated.
- Most (64%) respondents wanted borders to open at 90% of the eligible population vaccinated.
- Only 44% believed that future COVID-19 outbreaks in Tasmania would be managed well
- Most (64%) respondents wanted borders to open at 90% of the eligible population vaccinated.
- The Tasmanian health system not coping and the risk to the vulnerable were the most common concerns once borders open. Most respondents (84%) agreed that all visitors to the state should be vaccinated.
- 68% agreed that the vaccinated should be able to live with fewer restrictions than the unvaccinated.

Methodology

The Tasmania Project fifth general survey (TTP5) ran between September 24th and October 4th 2021. 1200 adult Tasmanian residents completed the survey.

Over half (62%) of respondents identified as female, 27% as male. We have not weighted findings against Tasmanian demographics for this report.

Only 2% of respondents were aged 18-24, 17% 25-44, 45% 45-64 and 37% 65+.

Just over a quarter (28%) have a Bachelor's Degree, 12% have no post-school qualifications and 7% have a doctorate.

The largest proportion of respondents (48%) resided in Greater Hobart, 21% in the North West and West, 12% in the Regional South, 11% in the Regional North, and 9% in Launceston.

Table 1: Sample demographics, respondents to TTP5, n and %.

	n	%
Gender		
Male	329	30.3
Female	736	68.0
Prefer not to say/self-describe	18	1.6
Age		
18-24	21	2.0
25-44	178	16.6
45-64	483	44.9
65+	393	36.6
Education level		
High school	125	11.5
Advanced Diploma, Certificate	212	19.6
Bachelor's degree or above	747	68.9
Region		
Greater Hobart	516	47.8
Regional South	126	11.7
Launceston	95	8.8
Regional North	121	11.2
North West and West	221	20.5

Life in the second year of COVID-19

Throughout The Tasmania Project, we've asked people about various ways the pandemic has affected their life and perspective, their access to essentials and supports, and their beliefs about the future. Many of these statements were asked again in TTP5.

Figure 1 outlines the proportion of respondents to TTP5 who agree, are neutral, or disagree with statements related to COVID-19 and their perspectives on life. Half (50%) of respondents agreed that COVID-19 had made them reconsider their life priorities, and 43% agreed that their life priorities had changed as a result of the pandemic (an increase from around one third of respondents to the second general survey which closed in June 2020).

While 60% of respondents agreed that they were enjoying a slower pace of life at the beginning of the pandemic (April/May 2020), this proportion was lower at 41% in the present survey. Concerns about the prospective impact of the pandemic on mental health were quite prominent in surveys and interviews conducted in the first half of 2020; in this survey, towards the end of 2021, 30% of respondents agreed that the pandemic had negatively affected their mental health.

At the beginning of the pandemic, 30% of respondents said they were increasing contact with family and friends. In TTP5, only 14% and 12% of respondents agreed that they have more contact with their family and friends, respectively, than before the pandemic.

In terms of differences in the impact of the pandemic on respondents' lives and perspectives by demographics, higher proportions of women, younger respondents, and those living in the North West and West than men, older respondents and those living in other regions agreed that they had reconsidered their life priorities, that their life priorities had changed, and that their mental health had been negatively impacted because of the pandemic.

Women, 25-44 year olds and those in the Regional South and Regional North were more likely to agree that they were enjoying a slower pace of life compared to before the pandemic. Higher proportions of younger respondents and those living in the Regional North and the North and North West agreed that they had more contact with family, and more 18-24 year olds than those in other age categories agreed that they had more contact with friends than before the pandemic.

Figure 1 also outlines level of agreement from respondents to statements about access to essentials and supports. The vast majority agreed that they had the devices they needed to connect to the internet at home (96%) and reliable access to the internet at home (91%). This is higher than earlier surveys where 72% agreed that their internet was fast enough for their needs, and 73% agreed that their internet was reliable. In line with previous results, most (95%) respondents agreed that they felt safe at home.

Figure 1: Proportion of respondents in each category of agreement with selected statements about their life and the pandemic (left) and access to essentials and supports (right)

Figure 2: Proportion of respondents (n=1008) who have undertaken selected activities, in person, in 2021

Just under one in five (19%) agreed that they cannot do the things they want to because of their health and, similar to previous surveys, 15% agreed that they could not access the health and support services they need.

With regard to demographic differences, younger respondents and those living in the Regional South and North West and West were more likely to agree that they had not been able to access the health and support services they need. Lower proportions of those in the Regional South and Regional North than in other regions agreed that they had reliable access to the internet at home, and lower proportions of those in Launceston than in other regions agreed that they had the devices they need to connect to the internet at home.

Higher proportions of men, older respondents, and a slightly higher proportion of those living in Launceston and the North and North West agreed that they cannot do the things they want because of their health.

The end of 2020 through 2021 has seen easing of many restrictions, enabling Tasmanians to engage in activities that were not accessible for much of 2020. We asked whether they had attended certain events and activities in person in 2021. Figure 2 outlines the proportion of respondents who had participated in each activity or event. Visiting a national park or reserve was most common, with 76% of respondents indicating that they had

attended in person in 2021, followed by bushwalking (63%), and the cinema/movies (48%). A good portion of respondents had attended an art exhibition/gallery (44%), live performance (43%), and museum (41%). Just under 1 in 4 respondents had attended a launch/opening (24%) or gone camping (24%), 23% had attended a festival, and 23% had attended a public lecture. One in five (21%) had attended a sporting match and only 12% had been recreational fishing.

Higher proportions of those in the Regional South and the Regional North than in other regions had visited a national park or reserve; more women, those aged 25-64 years and those in the Regional South had been bushwalking. Men, younger people, and those in Launceston were more likely to have attended a sporting match. More respondents aged 25-44 years and in Launceston and the Regional South had gone camping, and higher proportions of women, older respondents, and people in Greater Hobart and the Regional South reported attending an art exhibition/gallery.

The highest proportion of museum attendees were among women, people not in the 45-64 age category and people in Launceston, the Regional North and Greater Hobart; festival attendees were more likely to be younger and from Greater Hobart, Launceston and the Regional North; and women, those aged 25-64 years, and those in Greater Hobart and Launceston were more likely to have attended a

live performance in person in 2021. Higher proportions of women, younger respondents, and those living in Greater Hobart and Launceston reported going to the cinema/movies, men, 18-24 year olds and those in Greater Hobart and the Regional South were more likely to have attended a public lecture, and 25-64 year olds and those in Greater Hobart, Launceston and the Regional North were more likely to have attended a launch/opening. Recreational fishing was most commonly reported by men, younger respondents, and those in the Regional South.

The survey also asked some questions about concerns and thoughts about life in Tasmania and Australia (see Figure 3). A substantial majority (87%) agreed that they are concerned about the rise of political unrest/extremism in Australia. Almost two-thirds (65%) agreed that they want a different Tasmania to emerge from this crisis, and 63% agreed that they were not confident that we will ever have the same freedoms again. People were mixed on whether they had the opportunity to influence decisions on Tasmania's future: 24% agreed that they did, 38% were neutral and 39% disagreed.

Women, older respondents, and those in regions other than the Regional North were more likely to agree that they were concerned about the rise of political unrest/extremism in Australia; higher proportions of respondents aged over 25 years and those in Launceston and the North West and West agreed that they were not confident that we would ever have the same freedoms again; and women, those aged under 65 and those in regions other than the Regional

North were more likely to agree that they want a different Tasmania to emerge from this crisis. A higher proportion of those in the Regional North than in other regions felt they had the opportunity to influence decisions about Tasmania's future.

Personal COVID-19 safe practices

TTP5 asked respondents the extent to which they agreed with a number of statements about their COVID-19 safe (hereafter COVID-safe) practices. Several of these statements were also asked in the fourth general survey (29th April – 12 May 2021), and the proportions of respondents who agreed with each statement have remained very stable between the two surveys.

Overall, respondents indicated strong agreement with COVID-safe practices (see Figure 4): 85% agreed or strongly agreed (31% and 54, respectively) that they would wear a mask in public to limit the spread of COVID-19 and 80% agreed or strongly agreed (34% and 46%, respectively) that they would get tested for COVID-19 if they showed mild symptoms. Most respondents disagreed (26%) or strongly disagreed (59%) that they did *not* always check in to public venues for contact tracing. Similarly, most respondents disagreed (28%) or strongly disagreed (62%) that they would avoid being tested for COVID-19 so they do not have to self-isolate.

Despite strong indications that respondents are currently engaging in COVID-safe practices, the majority (85%) agreed or strongly agreed (35% and 50%, respectively) that they would be more vigilant with their COVID-safe practices once borders opened.

Figure 3: Proportion of respondents in each category of agreement with selected statements about life in Tasmania and Australia

Somewhat in line with this, 43% of respondents agreed (35%) or strongly agreed (8%) that they were more complacent with COVID-safe practices than they were at the beginning of the pandemic (though 42% disagreed with this statement to some extent).

Responses were mixed when it came to avoiding contact with visitors to Tasmania in case they have COVID-19, with roughly one third of respondents agreeing, one third disagreeing, and one third neither agreeing nor disagreeing. Similarly, while most (60%) respondents agreed to some extent that they were comfortable telling others to comply with COVID-safe practices, 21% neither agreed nor disagreed, and 19% disagreed to some extent.

Demographic differences in COVID-safe practices

Examining differences in responses about COVID-safe practices by gender (see Table 2) reveal that largely similar proportions of male and female respondents agreed or strongly agreed about their personal COVID-safe practices. A higher proportion of women than men (89% versus 77%) indicated that they would wear a face mask in public to limit the spread of COVID-19; slightly more men than women (44% versus 41%) agreed that they were more complacent about COVID-safe practices than they were at the start of the pandemic; and more women (36%) than men (31%) agreed that they avoid being in contact with visitors to Tasmania

in case they have COVID-19.

Examining differences by age, a slightly lower proportion of younger respondents (18-24 years) than those in other age categories agreed or strongly agreed that they would wear a mask to limit the spread of COVID-19 (81% of 18-24 year olds versus >85% in all other age categories). Just over two-thirds (67%) of people aged 25-44 years versus 76% of 18-24 year olds, 78% of 45-64 year olds and 88% of those aged 65 and above agreed that they'd get tested for COVID-19 if they had mild symptoms.

Younger respondents (18-24 years) and those aged 65 years and above were more comfortable telling others to comply with COVID-safe practices (76% and 68%, respectively) than those 'in the middle' (49% of 25-44 year olds and 56% of 45-64 year olds).

Younger respondents were more likely than those in other age categories to agree that they did not always check in for contact tracing, and those aged 25-44 years were more likely than those in other age categories to agree that they had become complacent in their personal COVID-safe practices relative to the beginning of the pandemic, and to agree that they would avoid being tested so they didn't have to self-isolate. A higher proportion of those aged 18-24 years than those in other age categories agreed that they avoid visitors to Tasmania in case they have COVID-19, and that they would be more vigilant with their COVID-safe practices once borders opened.

Figure 4: Proportion of respondents in each category of agreement with selected statements about their personal COVID-safe practices

There were no marked differences in COVID-safe practices by region: a very high proportion (92%) of those in the Regional North agreed that they would wear a face mask to limit the spread (versus 80-85% of those in other regions). A higher proportion of respondents from Launceston than those from other regions agreed that they did not always check in to public venues for contact tracing, and those in Greater Hobart and Launceston were more likely to agree that they had become complacent in their COVID-safe practices relative to the start of the pandemic.

Table 2: Proportion of respondents who agreed or strongly agreed with statements about personal COVID-safe practices, by gender¹

	Females	Males
I would wear a face mask in public to limit the spread of COVID-19 (n=1085)	88.9%	76.9%
If I showed mild symptoms of COVID-19, I would be tested (n=1084)	80.4%	81.1%
I feel comfortable telling people to comply with COVID-19 safe practices (n=1084)	60.3%	58.8%
I do NOT always check in to public venues for contact tracing (n=1083)	8.5%	16.8%
I would avoid being tested for COVID-19 so I do not have to self-isolate while waiting for results (n=1083)	4.3%	8.3%
I am more complacent about COVID-19 safe practices than I was at the start of the pandemic (n=1085)	40.9%	44.4%
I avoid being in contact with visitors to Tasmania in case they have COVID-19 (n=1083)	36.4%	30.5%
When the borders open, I will be more vigilant with COVID-19 safe practices (n=1083)	86.3%	83.0%

¹Some respondents chose to self-describe or not specify their gender. To preserve confidentiality and avoid skewing of the data due to the smaller size of these respondents, only those who identified as female or male are included in the above table

Vaccination

The majority (92%) of respondents who answered the question about whether they were vaccinated (n=1168) had been vaccinated, and 90% of those were fully vaccinated having received two doses. There was no marked difference in the proportion of men versus women that had been vaccinated and, as expected given the vaccine rollout, the proportion of people vaccinated increased in each age category (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: Proportion of respondents who were fully or partially vaccinated against COVID-19, by age category

In terms of proportion of respondents who were vaccinated, by region; Greater Hobart had the highest proportion of respondents who were vaccinated (96%), followed by Regional North (94%), Regional South (93%), Launceston (88%), then the North West and West (87%).

We asked respondents to select up to three main reasons that they chose to get vaccinated. Figure 6 indicates the proportion who selected each reason. The most common reasons for both male and female respondents were to help prevent the spread of COVID-19 in the community, to protect themselves, to protect their friends and family, and because they support vaccination/ immunisation programs in general. A higher proportion of females than males selected that helping to prevent the spread of COVID-19 in the community was a main reason for getting the vaccine (75% of females versus 66% of males) and to protect their friends and family (63% of females versus 59% of males), while a higher proportion of males (76%) than females (72%) selected protecting themselves as a main reason for getting the vaccination.

Examining reasons for getting vaccinated by age, younger respondents were more likely than older respondents to select protecting their friends and family as a main reason for getting vaccinated, while older respondents were more

Figure 6: Proportion (%) of respondents who were fully or partially vaccinated that identified selected reasons for having the vaccine, by gender (n=1014)

likely than younger respondents to select protecting themselves and helping to prevent the spread of COVID-19 in the community as main reasons for vaccination.

There were no marked differences between regions with respect to reasons for vaccination, with the exception of returning to life as it was before the pandemic: 30% of those who were vaccinated and residing in the North West and West and 26% of those in Launceston versus 14% of those in the Regional South, 18% of those in the Regional North and 20% of those in Greater Hobart selected returning to life as it was before the pandemic as main reasons for getting vaccinated.

Of those who were *not* vaccinated, 22% said they intend to be vaccinated, 6% could not be vaccinated for medical reasons, 5% had been unable to get an appointment, and 1% said they don't know if they're eligible. Just over one third (34%) of those who answered the question about why they were not vaccinated (n=94) said they do not want to be vaccinated.

We asked those who did not want to be vaccinated to identify selected reasons why not. Figure 7 illustrates the proportion of people who

"Because I am being forced to"
"Civic solidarity - protecting others"
"I have 3 risk factors"
"Because I want to go back to work and work primarily with children."

selected each reason (note: these results should be interpreted with caution due to the small sample size. Accordingly, we do not disaggregate by gender, age or region of residence).

Concerns about side effects (75%), safety (the vaccines needing more testing; 63%), and efficacy (lack of belief that the vaccine will prevent the spread; 59%) were the most common reasons for not getting the vaccination, followed by mistrust of the manufacturing companies (41%) and government (34%). No respondents selected inconvenient location or fear of needles as reasons for not getting the COVID-19 vaccination.

"I have been waiting for Moderna - My chemist is waiting for federal approval - I will be one of the first in the door when they have it."

We asked respondents with children under 16 years whether their children had been vaccinated. Of the 195 respondents who indicated that they had children under 16 years, 5% said their children were fully vaccinated, 11% partly vaccinated, 48% reported an intention for them to be vaccinated, and 10% did not want their children to be vaccinated. Recoding responses from the 'other' option, 18% of parents with children aged under 16 years indicated that their children were under 12 years and were therefore not yet eligible for the vaccine.

Figure 7: Proportion (%) of respondents who were choosing not to receive the vaccine that identified selected reasons for not having the vaccine (n=32)

Perspectives on COVID-19 and COVID-19 vaccinations

TTP5 also gauged perspectives on COVID-19 and the COVID-19 vaccination. Figure 8 outlines the proportion of respondents who agreed, disagreed or were neutral about selected statements about COVID-19 and COVID-19 vaccinations. The vast majority (87%) disagreed that COVID-19 was *not* as dangerous as health authorities claim. Similarly, 84% disagreed that vaccinations generally do more harm than good.

Most respondents agreed that they understand enough about the COVID-19 vaccines and the vaccination program (85%); that they have enough knowledge about the possible side effects of the vaccine (84%); that they encourage family and friends to be vaccinated (88%); and that they are concerned about members of the community choosing not to be vaccinated (83%).

When it came to making vaccines mandatory, responses were a little more distributed across categories: 56% agreed that vaccination should be mandatory, 23% were neutral, and 22% disagreed. Only 14% of respondents agreed that they were

worried about workplaces making vaccination mandatory.

There were very few differences between males' and females' perspectives on COVID-19 and COVID-19 vaccinations. A higher proportion of female respondents (90%) than male respondents (81%) disagreed that COVID-19 was *not* as dangerous as health authorities claim. More men (13%) than women (8%) were neutral on whether they had enough information about the COVID-19 vaccine, and women's responses were more mixed than men's on the topic of making vaccines mandatory: 63% of men versus 54% of women agreed that vaccination should be mandatory, 25% of women versus 17% of men were neutral, and similar proportions disagreed.

Similarly, there were few differences in respondents' perspectives on COVID-19 and vaccinations based on their age. The question of whether vaccinations should be mandatory attracted the most discrepancy in responses such that level of agreement increased with age: 67% of those aged 65 years and above, 52% of 45-64 year olds, 47% of 25-44 year olds and 33% of 18-24 year

olds agreed that vaccinations should be mandatory. A slightly smaller proportion of younger respondents (aged 18-24 years) than those in other age categories agreed that they understood enough about the COVID-19 vaccines and vaccination program, and that they were concerned about members of the community choosing not to be vaccinated.

Examining differences in COVID-19 and vaccination opinions by region, there were some slight differences. A higher proportion of those in Launceston (13%) and the Regional North (14%) agreed that vaccinations generally do more harm than good, compared with Hobart (9%) and the Regional South (9%).

More respondents in Launceston (19%) and the North and North West (23%) than in other regions (10% in Greater Hobart, 12% in the Regional South, 12% in the Regional North) were worried about workplaces making

vaccinations mandatory. A lower proportion of those in the North and North West (47%), Regional South (51%) and Regional North (51%) than in Greater Hobart (62%), and Launceston (56%) to agree that vaccines should be mandatory.

Those in the North and North West were less likely than those in other regions to agree that they encourage friends and family to get vaccinated, and less likely to be concerned about members of the community choosing not to be vaccinated.

Those in Greater Hobart (87%) and the Regional North (85%) were most concerned about members of the community choosing not to get vaccinated.

Figure 8: Proportion (%) of respondents in each category of agreement (agree, neutral, disagree) with selected statements about COVID-19 and the COVID-19 vaccination

Borders and safety

Recent months have seen different proposals at state and federal levels of government about when borders should open. TTP5 asked respondents when they believe borders should open, how safe they feel in Tasmania and the role that borders play in that sense of safety, and their beliefs and concerns once borders open.

Figure 9: When should Tasmanian borders reopen? (n=1179)

As Figure 9 illustrates, the majority of respondents (64%) believe that borders should reopen once 90% of the eligible population has been vaccinated, and 19% believe that borders should re-open at 80% vaccinated. Some (13%) believe that borders should remain closed and a small proportion (4%) believe that borders should open immediately.

There were no differences in beliefs about when borders should open between male and female respondents or those from different regions. More than one third (35%) of respondents aged 18-24 years believe that borders should remain closed (versus 9% of those aged 65+ years, 14% of those aged 45-64 years and 19% of those aged 25-44 years), though it must be noted that only twenty respondents age 18-24 years answered this question.

Figure 10: Thinking about world events, please indicate how safe you feel in Tasmania (n=1190)

With regard to safety in light of world events, the vast majority of respondents reported that they feel safe (42%) or very safe (56%) in Tasmania. Just shy of three quarters (74%) of people said that border restrictions influenced how safe they felt 'a lot'. Figures 10 and 11, below, illustrate the breakdown of responses to these questions.

Male respondents were more likely than females to report feeling unsafe or very unsafe in Tasmania (though only a very small number of men and women indicated that they felt this way), but there were no differences between men and women when it came to the influence of border restrictions on feelings of safety. There were no differences between respondents of different age categories on feelings of safety, nor of the influence of borders on feelings of safety. There were slight regional differences in feelings of safety between regions, such that a higher proportion of those in the North West and West than in other regions reported feeling unsafe or very unsafe (though, once again, very small numbers of respondents from any region reported feeling unsafe or very unsafe).

Figure 11: To what extent do border restrictions influence how safe you feel in Tasmania? (n=1195)

Figure 12 presents the proportion of respondents who agreed or strongly agreed with selected statements about COVID-19 and Tasmania. Most (88%) respondents trusted scientists to provide reliable information about COVID-19, and two thirds (67%) trusted government and officials to do the same. Only around half (53%) of respondents agreed or strongly agreed that they understand what the Tasmanian Government is doing to prepare for future cases or outbreaks, and less than half (44%) felt that future COVID-19 outbreaks in Tasmania will be managed well.

A minority (15%) of respondents felt that Tasmania has adequate resources to manage a COVID-19 outbreak, and only 9% agreed that the Tasmanian Government has been too slow to ease COVID-19 restrictions.

Figure 12: Proportion (%) of respondents who agreed or strongly agreed with selected statements about COVID-19 and Tasmania

Similar proportions of male and female respondents agreed with each of the statements in figure 12 – a slightly lower proportion of women than men agreed that the Tasmanian Government has been too slow to ease restrictions, a slightly higher proportion of women than men believed that future outbreaks in Tasmania would be managed well and that they understood what the Tasmanian Government was doing to prepare for them, though fewer women than men felt Tasmania has adequate resources to manage an outbreak.

Differences by age categories were also relatively minor: respondents aged 25-44 years were more likely than those in other age categories to agree that the Tasmanian Government has been too slow to ease restrictions and that Tasmania has adequate resources to manage future outbreaks, while a lower proportion of older respondents (45+ years) than younger respondents (<45 years) believed that future outbreaks would be managed well.

In terms of differences between regions, a higher proportion of respondents in Launceston and the North West and West

than in other regions agreed that that the Tasmanian Government has been too slow to ease restrictions, those in the North West and West were less likely than those in other regions to trust scientists or the government to provide reliable information about COVID-19, and were more likely to agree that Tasmania has adequate resources to manage an outbreak. Only 43.2% of respondents from Launceston (relative to 52.8% of respondents overall) agreed that they understand what the Tasmanian Government is doing to prepare for future outbreaks.

Concerns about COVID-19 and the future

Respondents were asked about their concerns about the COVID-19 pandemic and, in particular, their concerns once borders open. One statement put to respondents was “I am more concerned about the economic impacts than the health impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic”. The majority (65%) disagreed or strongly disagreed, around one in five (19%) neither agreed nor disagreed, and 16% agreed or strongly agreed.

A higher proportion of male respondents than female, younger (<45 years) than older (45+ years), and those from the North West and West and Launceston than other regions agreed that they were more concerned with the economic than health impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Figure 13: I am more concerned about the economic impacts than the health impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic (n=1198)

The survey also asked respondents to indicate their level of concern about certain things once borders re-open. The majority of respondents held some level of concern (from slight to extreme) about all of the statements. Of particular concern to respondents was the Tasmanian health system not coping – 69% were extremely concerned and 18% were moderately concerned, followed by the risk to vulnerable people and/or those who cannot be vaccinated: 63% were extremely concerned and 23% moderately concerned. Risks of cases and deaths in the community were also common

concerns once borders open, with 79% and 78% of respondents, respectively, extremely or moderately concerned.

Respondents were least concerned about getting COVID-19 themselves (though 26% still cited extreme concern about this); 42% were extremely concerned about children under 12 years getting COVID-19 because they have not been vaccinated, and about their friends and family getting COVID-19.

Concerns that not enough of the population being vaccinated were common, though level of concern was more divided between extreme, moderate, and slight than with other issues. Figure 14 depicts the proportions of respondents across each category of concern for each issue when borders open.

Across all statements, a higher proportion of male respondents compared to female were 'not at all concerned'. Differences in levels of concern by age categories varied, and must be interpreted with caution because of the low number of people in the 18-24 years category.

Nevertheless, younger respondents (<45 years) were less concerned than older respondents (≥45 years) about getting COVID-19 themselves and about enough of the population being vaccinated. A higher proportion of those aged 25-44 years than those in any of the other age

categories reported that they were 'not at all concerned' about children (under 12 years) getting COVID-19 because they have not been vaccinated.

A higher proportion of respondents aged 18-24 years than those from other age categories were concerned about the risk to vulnerable people and/or those who cannot be vaccinated, but also 'not at all' concerned about the risk of deaths in the community. Those aged 45-64 years were more concerned than those in other age categories about the Tasmanian health system not coping. Across all statements, a higher proportion of those in the North West and West than in other regions reported that they were 'not at all' concerned. A higher proportion of those in the Regional North than in other regions were concerned about getting COVID-19 themselves.

Respondents were also asked an open ended question "Do you have any other concerns?" A total of 258 people wrote a response to this question, and we categorised these responses thematically. It is important to note that the prominence of a theme (or, indeed, the absence of a theme) does not necessarily reflect the importance of the theme to all respondents, as the responses are only from

Figure 14: Proportion (%) of respondents in each category of concern about certain things, once borders open.

those who chose to write a response and are only in response to the single prompt listed above. Nevertheless, the results provide some interesting insights into the concerns of respondents once borders open. Despite being an option in the question set depicted in Figure 14, concerns about the health system were the most frequently mentioned 'other' concern in people's responses to the open-ended question (n=36). These were primarily generalised concerns about the health system being "overwhelmed", "a shambles", having "zero capacity for any more sick people", "not coping", and hospitals being "already in crisis".

Within the health system theme, several respondents were worried about delays to elective surgeries and COVID-19-related health care use preventing people from being able to treat existing and emerging health conditions such as cancer. The state of the healthcare workforce was also a concern for some who cited overwork and stress, and others identifying the casualisation of the health workforce, particularly in the aged care and disability sectors, as a concern once borders open.

Some respondents articulated actions that they believed Tasmania (or, specifically, the Tasmanian Government) should undertake:

"Our current hospitals and available doctors are not coping with normal hospital requirements. Until that is fixed we should be very conservative in allowing free movement in a COVID-19 world."

"We MUST remain closed until 90% are vaxed, and preferably until children under 12 are also vaxed."

"The Tasmanian Government needs to prioritise the health system and health services as they are not coping with the current level of diseases in the population and admissions into the hospitals. Staff are exhausted and stressed and need much more support."

Civil liberties and freedoms were the second most common concerns (n=27), both from people who were concerned about losing the liberties associated with being a COVID-free state and from people who were concerned that COVID-19 was being used as a platform for government encroachment on citizens' rights.

"Losing the COVID-free status of Tasmania may mean we are losing some of the freedoms we have been enjoying and more restrictions being introduced"

"Losing the freedoms we have with NO COVID in the community"

"I am significantly more concerned about excessive government controls than covid"

"I am more concerned about what governments are doing to people and businesses than Covid-19. Personal freedoms have been trampled upon"

Poor leadership at state and federal government levels was also a common theme (n=21). The sources of people's disappointment with leadership varied, including things like the (mis)management of the health system, the aforementioned encroachment on civil liberties, poor and/or inconsistent communication about COVID-19, and general concerns of "corruption" and "incompetence".

"If Australia follows American political leads over an extended period will the premier grow a Trump Mullet?"

Some people were concerned that the government was sowing civil unrest by creating a "two-tiered society" and "spreading hate and propaganda between the vaccinated and unvaccinated". Some also blamed the media for this rhetoric and divide, while others placed blame on citizens who were responding to the rhetoric with disobedience and violence.

The risk to the vulnerable was also a common theme. These concerns included that the vulnerable – who for some people were those in rural and isolated places, for others were older Tasmanians, those with disability, the young, or just "the vulnerable" - had not had adequate access to vaccinations or were unable to be vaccinated. The lack of plan for management of COVID-19 in relation to the vulnerable was also a concern, and intersected with the previous theme of poor leadership:

"Fine words about targeting vulnerable groups, consistently under-delivered"

"Extremely concerned is not enough re those who cannot be vaccinated - there seems to be no real plan or proposed management for the vulnerable, for whatever medical reason, cannot be vaccinated. 90%, or even higher, will not help these people when vaccinated people have Covid and are also infectious but asymptomatic and possibly unaware they are a walking death sentence for others"

Concerns about the inadequacy and/or inconsistency of COVID-safe measures, both from the perspective of their conception and implementation by state leaders and from the perspective of individual compliance, were also common (n=20). Some of these were general concerns such as “non-compliance”, “how easy it may be to cheat the covid regulations”, and that “Tasmanians have become too complacent”. Other concerns were niche such as public bathrooms not having Check In TAS QR codes. Several of these concerns were all-encompassing of the government’s management of the pandemic:

“We seem stuck with the same government response as at the start of Covid. Let’s use rapid testing! Vaccine passport please. And why isn’t the Cabin Park at the airport a quarantine facilities already?”

“The unethical, inhumane & unconstitutional refusal of all Australian governments to provide rapid antigen testing & treatments as a [sic] inarguable alternative to untested & dangerous vaccines. Also outraged that Novavax is not already here & available to whomever wants it”

“While I am concerned about borders reopening, I think there are measures we could implement to ensure COVID-19 stays out, including testing of visitors, mask wearing, temperature testing, open air events etc... think the government need to be very cautious”

Various concerns relating to aspects of the vaccines and vaccination were common. Many of these related to vaccine effectiveness (n=19), though from many different angles. Some people were concerned about vaccination targets being politically-set, arbitrary and/or incorrectly calculated (e.g. ‘eligible’ rather than total population) rather than based on accurate health advice. Several were concerned that the vaccination does not stop the spread of COVID-19; some because of concerns about illness for themselves and/or their community (particularly the vulnerable), some for the health system, and some believed that its inability to stop the spread renders the vaccine pointless. Some were concerned about the long-term effectiveness of the vaccination, and 6 people mentioned booster shots – concerns about a lack of plan for implementing them and insufficient vaccine stock.

Twelve respondents mentioned concerns about the population, particularly health workers, but also friends and family and/or the community generally, being unwilling to be vaccinated. An additional 11 respondents specifically referred to concerns about “anti-vaxxers” – including their causing of civil unrest

and/or violence, spreading of misinformation, “clogging up” the health system once borders open, and creating health risks for the community via their choice to not be vaccinated. Some (n=9) respondents were concerned that those who wanted to be vaccinated, particularly the young, will not have had enough time to do so before borders open.

Thirteen respondents mentioned concerns about the economic impacts, either of having the border shut or once borders open. Some of these were personal – concerns about their business suffering as a result of the border shutting, that their industry could not operate with the restrictions required once borders open, or about losing their job because they don’t want to be vaccinated. Respondents had varying perspectives on the health versus economy debate:

“Whilst Tasmania’s Lock Out has detrimentally affected businesses, allowing Covid into the State would multiply that impact and severely overload our health care system that is already under stress”

“It is hard balancing the economy versus health dichotomy, and it may be that it is a false one, as keeping an economy closed or partially closed does have health consequences for large parts of the population”

One respondent articulated their ambivalence about opening up borders and the economy quite plainly:

“The impact on business if we don’t open.. but I don’t want Tas to open!!”

Some of those who were concerned about economic impacts advocated for balance:

“Of course I am concerned about friends and family getting covid but there has to be a balance. Social, mental health and economic damage must be a consideration.”

“My main concern relates to the other health and economic impacts which are increasing rapidly while we remain closed. In particular I am concerned with mental health impacts, domestic violence, delayed elective surgery, loss of income, loss of businesses, loss of housing. All these things are happening because we have a singular focus on covid.”

“We need to open our state and our nation to the rest of the world to not be left behind socially economically and mentally.”

Several (n=7) respondents felt that the singular focus on COVID-19 was to the detriment of other issues, particularly the natural environment and/or climate change (n=4), but also issues around international relations and health.

Intersecting with several other themes, in particular poor leadership and the health system, several respondents (n=10) articulated concerns about the economy being prioritised above people:

“Concerns that the government will eventually care only about the economy rather than people”

“Fear that perceived economic concerns will eventually override health concerns - especially under the influence of hard right and extremist religious people and their leaders.”

“My greatest concern is that the economic damage will be seen by decision makers as the most important area to focus on rather than the health of Tasmanians.”

“Stupid politicians who think it is okay for me to die so the economy can make a buck.”

Twelve respondents expressed concern about the mental health impacts of the pandemic. Some were concerned about the mental health impacts of restrictions to socialisation, some of the mental health impacts of opening borders and having COVID-19 spread through the community, and some of the mental health impacts of the general sense of uncertainty and stress brought on by the pandemic:

“Uncertainty has created a worried society/community at the least, at the most, one full of anxiety and feelings of no hope for the future”

Almost equal numbers of respondents expressed a desire for borders to open up (or concerns that they won't) (n=12) and for borders to stay closed (n=11). Among those who were keen for borders to open up, seeing friends and family was a prominent reason, as was the economy. Among a few there was a general sense of being “fed up” and feeling like people had had enough time to be vaccinated:

“People have had plenty of time to be vaccinated if they are not by now that is on them”

“People must take responsibility for themselves @ 80% we must be set free to live a new normal life”

The main driver for people who wanted to keep borders closed was a desire to keep COVID-19 out:

“you can't get covid in your house if you don't let it in”

However, many respondents (including many of those who expressed a desire for borders to stay closed) recognised that borders would open and wanted various conditions fulfilled to make that safe for Tasmanians, such as waiting until a sufficient proportion of the total Tasmanian population were vaccinated, processes for ensuring visitor compliance (such as vaccination and quarantine) were in place, the health system was in better shape and that the decision to open up was based on evidence rather than political expedience.

The role of vaccination in moving forward

Respondents were also asked questions about the role of vaccination in moving through COVID-19, in particular about restrictions on those who are not vaccinated.

Figure 15 outlines the proportion of respondents who agreed, were neutral and disagreed with selected sentiments about vaccination. The substantial majority (87%) agreed that vaccination is the most important thing we can do to help protect ourselves and our community and 87% agreed that vaccination is the most important thing we can do to help enable Tasmania to safely reopen its borders. Similarly, 84% agreed that all visitors into the state should be fully vaccinated against COVID-19. Results were slightly more mixed about whether fully vaccinated people should be able to live with fewer restrictions than unvaccinated people. The majority (68%) agreed, but 17% were neutral and 5% disagreed.

More men than women agreed that all visitors into the state should be fully vaccinated against COVID-19 and that the fully vaccinated should be able to live with fewer restrictions than unvaccinated people. For each statement, the proportion of respondents who agreed increased with each age category (i.e. higher proportions of older people than younger people agreed with each statement). Lower proportions of those in the North West and West than in other regions agreed that all visitors into the state should be fully vaccinated. More people in Launceston, the Regional North and Greater Hobart than in the North West and Wets and Regional South agreed that fully vaccinated people should be able to live

with fewer restrictions than unvaccinated people. Launceston and the North West and West had the lowest proportion of respondents who agreed that vaccination is the most important thing we can do to help protect ourselves and our community and that vaccination is the most important thing we can do to help enable Tasmania to safely open its borders.

Respondents were also asked whether they agreed that unvaccinated people should be banned from selected activities and events. The vast majority of respondents agreed that unvaccinated people should be banned from working with vulnerable people (89%) and from working in schools or childcare (81%). Almost three-quarters of respondents agreed that the unvaccinated should be banned from concerts and gigs (73%) and from large sporting events (73%). More respondents agreed that the unvaccinated should be banned from interstate travel than from travel outside of Australia (70% versus 65%).

Over two-thirds of respondents agreed that the unvaccinated should be banned from working in shared spaces (70%), going to the cinema (70%), community events (70%) and going to restaurants (67%). Essential services and activities, namely attending school or childcare and taking public transport, attracted lower levels of agreement for banning the unvaccinated at 65% and 62% respectively.

Attendance of religious gatherings was the activity that the lowest proportion of respondents agreed that the unvaccinated should be banned from, at 59%. Figure 16 outlines the proportion of respondents who agreed, were neutral, and disagreed with banning the unvaccinated from selected events and activities.

Across all events and activities, a greater proportion of male respondents, those aged 65 years and above, and those residing in Greater Hobart, compared to women, those in other age categories, and those residing in other regions, respectively, agreed that the unvaccinated people should be banned. There was generally more distribution across the three levels of agreement (agree, neutral, disagree) for younger people, especially those aged 25-44 years, than those aged 45 years and above. With the exception of travel – interstate and outside of Australia – those residing in the North and North West had the lowest proportion of respondents who agreed that the unvaccinated should be banned from activities and events.

Figure 15: Proportion (%) of respondents in each category of agreement about selected statements about COVID-19 vaccination.

Figure 16: Proportion (%) of respondents in each category of agreement (agree, neutral, disagree) about banning the unvaccinated from selected events and activities

Where next?

The fifth general survey of The Tasmania Project has provided some insights into what the second year of life during COVID-19 has looked like for people, and what their concerns and convictions are moving into the next phase of the pandemic.

In terms of life in the second year of the pandemic, fewer respondents than in earlier surveys were enjoying a slower pace of life and fewer agreed that they had more contact with their friends and family. This may reflect a return to conditions closer to those pre-pandemic. This was also somewhat reflected in respondents' in-person participation in events and activities – substantial portions of respondents had attended activities and events in person but, particularly for arts and cultural events, participation was lower than pre-pandemic levels reported in earlier surveys.

Most respondents were vaccinated, and most agreed that vaccination was the most important thing to do for community safety and safe reopening of the borders. Almost all (97%) respondents felt safe or very safe in Tasmania in light of world events, and three quarters said that border restrictions influenced their sense of safety 'a lot'. The majority of respondents selected 90% of the eligible population vaccinated as the point at which they believed borders should open.

Regarding borders opening, Tasmania's health system not coping and the risk to the vulnerable were the prevailing concerns once borders open.

Understanding what the government is doing to prepare for future COVID-19 outbreaks was quite low, with only 53% of respondents agreeing, and only 44% believing that future outbreaks in Tasmania will be managed well.

Moving forward, the majority of respondents (84%) believed that all visitors into the state should be fully vaccinated against COVID-19, though fewer agreed that the fully vaccinated should be able to live with fewer restrictions than unvaccinated people (68%).

There were differences in the proportion of respondents who agreed that the unvaccinated should be banned from events and activities, based on the activity. A strong majority (89%) agreed that the unvaccinated should be banned from working with vulnerable people and 81% agreed the unvaccinated should be banned from working in schools and childcare, while 62% agreed the unvaccinated should be banned from taking public transport and 65% agreed the unvaccinated should be banned from attending school or childcare.

Image: Getty Images.

The Tasmania Project will continue, providing insight into what is important to people in Tasmania, over time. Results from the qualitative and quantitative data provided by Tasmanian residents will be fed, with other data sources, into the Institute for Social Change's 'The Good Life Initiative'. The Good Life Initiative aims to present information from and about Tasmanian communities in ways that facilitate better decision making by all community stakeholders.